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Dear Mrs. Wilkens, dear Dr. Hofmann-Sieber,

Thank you for your order to identify/authenticate cell lines. We have created a DNA profile of 8 highly polymorphic sites of Short Tandem Repeats (STRs) for the detection of human cells from your samples using a nonaplex PCR. In addition, the samples were tested for the presence of DNA sequences from rats and hamsters.

For the identification of animal species, the samples were subjected to the cytochrome oxidase I (COI) DNA bar coding method. In case of murine samples we will try to trace murine samples to a specific mouse strain using a murine STR technology.

Results:

#	sample	parental/reference line	comment/match
1	GPTEC-T	unknown	COI Barcoding analysis revealed <i>Cavia porcellus</i> species, species-specific
2	C1 104	unknown	COI Barcoding analysis revealed <i>Cavia porcellus</i> species, species-specific

Both cell samples are free of human cells with a detection limit of 10^{-3} and animal cells from rat, Chinese and Syrian hamster with a detection limit of 10^{-5} . The samples are derived of pure Guinea Pig cell cultures.

The continuous cell line GPTEC-T (Guinea Pig Tracheal Epithelial Cells) is unknown, so far only primary GPTEC cells have been reported in the literature. Species determinations of samples 1 and 2 were performed using COI DNA Barcoding and reveal the authentic species of *Cavia porcellus* (domestic guinea pigs).

Based on a personal message from Dr. Hofmann-Sieber (email from 17.08.2018) we have performed a free-of-cost detection of the large antigen of Simian Virus-40 (largeT SV40). The result shows that although GPTEC-T carries the largeT SV40, this analysis is negative for the sample C1 104 (see attachments). Therefore, C1 104 is not a derivative of GPTEC-T cells.

The detection of largeT SV40 in GPTEC cells is a unique selling point, so that GPTEC-T must be regarded as unique among cell lines of the species *Cavia porcellus*.

An individualisation of animal cell lines often cannot be carried out due to the lack of suitable STR typing systems or is not possible in the case of rodent cells due to lack of genetic variability due to inbreeding.

With kind regards,

W. Dirks